

COMPUTATIONAL MODELING OF 3-D TEXTILE COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: A 3-D computational model was developed for property prediction and damage characterization of the 3-D complex-architected composites. The present model generated yarn-level microgeometries of complex yarn and resin-rich matrix material based on textile preforming processes by using a fiber-level digital element method, yarn smoothing, CAD solid modeling and finite element meshing. The model created 2-D and 3-D woven composites as well as triaxial braided composites. The yarn-level microgeometry model with multi-cell (20 by 10) 2-D woven composites was analyzed by a high-performance computational method with parallel clustered computers and a parallelly enhanced finite element structural analysis program. The present model provides a useful tool that integrates the fabrication process simulation with the stress/damage analysis modules. The method can be utilized for prediction of thermoelastic properties as well as the damage behavior that highly depends on the details of the local microstructure in the textile composites.

KEYWORDS: 3-D textile composites, micromechanics, yarn, matrix, parallel computation, finite element.

INTRODUCTION

Innovative weaving and braiding processes open up a new opportunity of making 3-D textile composites of significantly damage-tolerant structural response with design flexibility, durable joints, and near-net shape processing. Compared with unidirectional composites, interlacing of fiber bundles in textile composites prevents the growth of damage and hence provides an increase in toughness. Directional thermoelastic performance of these 3-D textile composites can be tailored as well through ever-evolving weaving technology.

To fully understand the mechanical behavior of the 3-D textile composites, it is essential to perform analyses such as prediction of effective material properties and characterization of damage initiation and growth. The effective material properties include elastic constants, thermal conductivity and coefficient of viscosity of fabric composites from the known material properties of the constituent phases. However, because of the complex fabric architecture, it is not easy to predict the mechanical properties of the 3-D textile composites compared to the 2-D ones such as 2-D woven composites [1, 2].

Furthermore, variability in the fabrication processes causes irregularity in weaving or braiding patterns in the 3-D textile composites. The irregularity in weaving or braiding patterns can seriously affect its thermoelastic behavior, especially damage initiation and failure progress. Therefore, effects of this fabrication irregularity must be quantified to certify these composites. In order to obtain the correct preform geometry (cross section as well as its path), various weaving or braiding process parameters, including tow tension, tow density, tow size, weaving or braiding patterns and fabrication irregularity (tow spacing, etc.), should be considered in the analysis of the 3-D textile composites.

The integration of the weaving/braiding-process simulation with the stress analysis will provide a methodology to directly assess the effect of fabrication parameters on the performance of the textile composites such as variable cross section of the reinforcing yarns, process-induced microcracking, fatigue life, damage progression, etc. The methodology will also provide a tool for probabilistic analysis of manufacturing variability, which has not been studied before.

The most challenging task of this study is the incorporation of the constitutive behavior of the reinforcing tows in the fabrication process, which causes the tow cross-section to change and deform with the weaving pattern. If the tow constitutive behavior is correctly modeled, it will be a pervasive tool integrating the fabrication irregularity with the performance of the next-generation composites.

In this work, a computational model was developed to determine the complex yarn profiles through simulation of the weaving and braiding processes. This preform geometry shall be integrated with a finite element analysis to perform stress analysis for design of the 3-D textile composites.

GENERATION OF 3-D COMPLEX TEXTILE ARCHITECTURES

The textile composites consist of two constituents of materials: fibers (or filaments) and matrix resin. The matrix resin exists both in the yarns (or tows) and in the resin-rich matrix area that fills the gaps between the yarns. With these constituents, the analysis of the textile composite materials and structures can be achieved in three different scales: fiber-level-, micro- and macro-scales. The fiber-level-scale analysis considers the fibers and resin constituents in the yarn as independent materials. The micro-scale approach homogenizes the fibers and the matrix resin in the yarn into a yarn material, and thus considers only two independent materials: the homogenized yarns and the resin-rich area. The homogenized yarn generally possesses orthotropic (or transversely isotropic) material properties because of the directionality of the fibers in the yarn. The macro-scale analysis considers the textile composites as completely homogeneous materials by further smearing the yarns and resin-rich matrix material.

While the macro-scale approach can be suitable for prediction of effective thermoelastic modulus properties, it masks large internal stresses associated with yarns and matrix interaction. Therefore, it is difficult to accurately predict pre-, ongoing, and post-damage behaviors of the textile composites since the damage highly depends on the details of the local microstructures in the textile composite. Furthermore, it is difficult to implement the effect of fabrication irregularity with the macro-scale approach compared to the micro-scale one that can consider the effect of inhomogeneous arrangement of yarns and matrix.

In this work, the complex yarn and matrix geometries in the 3-D complex-architected textile composites were formulated for the yarn-level numerical analysis by using a fiber-level digital element method, yarn smoothing, CAD solid modeling and finite element meshing.

Digital Element Simulation

A digital element (DE) method has been recently developed in order to simulate textile processes and fabric deformation [3, 4]. In the DE method, each fiber in a yarn is modeled as a digital element chain. The digital chain is composed of a set of short cylindrical bars (digital element) which are connected by frictionless pins (see Fig. 1 (a)). As the length of these DEs approaches zero, the pin-connected DE chain become fully flexible. Physically, each DE chain represents a flexible one dimensional entity with a circular cross section. Each yarn consists of many fibers, which is defined by an assembly of the digital element chains. The yarn is composed of typically thousands of fibers. However, 19-50 fibers are used to practically represent yarn cross section in the simulation.

Contact behavior among the digital chains (fibers) in the yarn can be represented by the contact of the nodes. As shown in Fig. 1 (b), the distance between two nodes is smaller than the diameter, a contact element will be placed between two nodes for the contact simulation. Using digital element analysis, both textile performing processes and fabric deformation can be modeled as a static or dynamic problem with boundary and/or initial conditions. Digital element simulation generates a fiber-based microgeometry.

Fig. 1. Schematics of (a) digital element chain and (b) contact of the digital chains.

Fig. 2 illustrates a procedure for the generation of a 3-D ply-to-ply woven geometry using the DE method. The fiber-based microgeometry is generated in the following five steps:

1. Yarn patterns are firstly recognized for a unit cell from the yarn architecture. It is then expanded in the x- and y-directions to form a yarn structure with the same topology as the fabric to be modeled, as shown in Fig. 2 (a). This is called as an “initial-guess geometry.” Each yarn is represented by a single digital rod-element chain.
2. An extended segment is added to the end of each yarn. An initial tension is assumed at the ends of the yarns. Using a fixed boundary condition, the fabric deforms under the initial extension, forming a shape as shown in Fig. 2 (b). The process is called “initial relaxation.”

3. The third step is called “fibering”. A yarn is discretized into approximately 29 fibers, as shown in Fig. 2 (c).
4. The fabric continues deforming under the initial extension, generating a fiber level microstructure as shown in Fig. 2 (d).
5. Finally, the extended edges were cut to form a unit-cell microstructure as shown in Fig. 2 (e).

Fig. 2. Schematics in generation of fiber-level microgeometry using the digital element simulation. (a) initial-guess geometry, (b) initial relaxation, (c) fibering, (d) microstructure after the final DE simulation and (e) unit-cell microstructure.

The DE analysis was employed to generate the microgeometries for four kinds of fabrics: 2-D plain woven fabric, tri-axial braided fabric, 3-D layer-to-layer woven fabric and 3-D

orthogonal woven fabric, which are shown in Fig. 3 (a), (b), (c) and (d), respectively. The latter two are 3-D woven fabrics that have reinforcement in the thickness direction [5].

Fig. 3. Various fabrics generated using the digital element method. (a) 2-D plain woven, (b) triaxial braided fabrics (c) 3-D layer-to-layer woven and (d) 3-D orthogonal woven.

Yarn-Surface Smoothing

The DE simulation provides fiber bundles for a yarn. However, we desire to have yarn-level microgeometry for the FE analysis, which consider discrete yarns and matrix subregions as homogeneous materials. Therefore, a step is need for a transition from the DE analysis to the FE analysis. The transition was made by smoothing the boundary formed by the fiber bundle. The transition step extracts the following information for the FE mesh: 1) yarn volumes to be meshed and 2) material axes along the yarn undulation. A step for smoothing yarn-surface boundaries was taken to achieve the transition.

The microgeometry generated by the DE analysis was transformed into the yarn-based description by the transition step, yarn-surface smoothing, as shown in Fig. 4. In order to derive the yarn cross-sectional boundary, a circle that is larger in diameter than the fiber diameter rolls along the outer edge of the fiber bundles of the yarn. The trajectory of contact points between the larger circle and the fibers then defines the cross-sectional boundary of the yarn. Many of the cross-sectional boundaries are generated along the yarn's undulatorily longitudinal direction, which will eventually form a yarn surface boundary for the FE analysis.

Fig. 4.
Define a yarn cross-sectional boundary geometry.

Geometric Manipulation

The microgeometry for 3-D textile composites obtained by the DE method and the surface smoothing went through another transition step, “geometric manipulation.” This step utilize CAD model to convert the yarn-based microgeometry into volume objects to be meshed for finite elements. In this work, the CAD capability that is implemented in ANSYS.

The previous steps provide the coordinates of points that consist of the surface of the yarns. These points became keypoints in the CAD model. Lines were drawn by connecting the keypoints. Mesh parameters such as number of subdivision or spacing size were assigned to these lines. Areas and volumes were subsequently defined by using the lines and areas, respectively. The yarn volumes were then meshed to have FE nodes and elements by using the automatic mesh generation routines in ANSYS.

The analysis of the textile composites needs to consider the undulation of the yarns. The undulation can be described by defining local coordinate systems along centroids of the yarn cross sections. One axis of the local coordinate system is parallel to the undulation, while the other two axes lie on a plane of the cross-section. The material axis will then be transformed to the local axes to describe the undulation.

Fig. 5 shows the schematic of the procedure to generate the microgeometry and FE model of a yarn by using the DE simulation, the surface smoothing, the CAD model and the FE model.

Two preform geometries for 3-D woven yarns were generated by using the present method. One has a layer-to-layer woven pattern, and the other has an orthogonal woven pattern, as shown in Fig. 6. The layer-to-layer and the orthogonal weave preforms consist of 44 and 68 warp, fill and/or stitching yarns, respectively.

The textile composites consist of not only the yarns but the matrix material. The matrix material fills the space between the yarns. The volumes for the matrix materials can be generated by using geometrical manipulation. First, a domain of the matrix regions is defined as a continuously homogeneous isotropic material. Then the previously defined yarn volumes were subtracted from the matrix domain by geometric subtraction, which can be achieved handily by using geometric manipulation functions that is implemented in ANSYS. After subtracting all yarn volumes, the remaining volumes would represent the matrix volumes, which will eventually be meshed for the FE analysis.

Fig. 5. Schematic of generating yarn geometry and FE model.

Fig. 6. Volume objects to be meshed for numerical analysis with microgeometries of 3-D woven fabrics. (a) layer-to-layer pattern and (b) orthogonal woven pattern.

HIGH-PERFORMANCE FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

The representative volume element (RVE) or unit cell of the 2-D textile composites can be formulated relatively simply. However, the RVE of the 3-D textile composites is much more complicated and contains many subvolumes for the yarns and matrix material. Therefore, the size of the considered problems becomes large with many degrees of freedom with many elements and nodes. Furthermore, the FE analysis requires the assembly and solution of system of equations which consumes more computer memories and solution time. Therefore, a single CPU high-performance machine may not be capable of handling the large size of the problems.

In this work, high-performance computation for the large size of the problem for the 3-D textile composites were performed with parallel clustered computers with multi CPU as well as a parallelly enhanced computer program for the FE analysis. The parallel clustered computers are composed of 32 nodes with Intel Xeon CPUs and 2 GBytes of memories. The nodes are connected parallelly and communicated through a gigabit ethernet router. Redhat Linux is used for the operating system and MPICH [6-8] is used for parallelization of the FE analysis program.

Nonzero components in a global stiffness matrix were stored in sparse-matrix format and distributed into the nodes of the clustered computers. PSPASES [9] (Parallel SPArse Symmetric direct Solver), an MPI-based parallel stand-alone library intended to solve the system of linear equations, is implemented in the FE program. By the distributed storage scheme of the global stiffness matrix into the multiple nodes as well as independent computational operations on the computers, not only can the large size of problems be solved, but the assembly and solution time can significantly be reduced. The scale-down of the memory and the solution time is the significant advantage of the parallel clustered computation.

A multi-cell the plain-woven composites were modeled and solved with the present method. The unit-cell of the plain-woven geometry for the yarns and matrix material were formulated with sinusoidal functions [10]. Then the unit-cell was duplicated 20 and 10 times in the warp and fill directions, respectively, as shown. Fig. 7 shows the FE meshes for the warp and fill yarns. The meshes for the resin-rich matrix regions are not shown in the figure. The multi-cell model was subjected to a bending deformation with a fixed boundary condition at one side of the edge and a uniform vertical displacement boundary condition at the other side of the edge. Fig. 8 shows the deformed shape and the vertical displacement field solution.

The 20 by 10 multi-cell model consists of 102,400 8-node solid elements with B-spline approximation shape functions [11]. The total number of degrees of freedom is 349,191 and total number of nonzeros in the global stiffness matrix in sparse matrix format is 25,508,115 before factorization of the stiffness matrix. Although the total number of nonzeros after the factorization is not recorded, it is common that the total nonzeros after factorization become significantly larger (more than 10 times) than the one before the factorization, and thus this problem could not be handled with the single-CPU machine. The total computational time with the 32 CPUs was approximately 30 minutes, among which the elapsed time for the solution of the global system of equations was approximately 4 minutes.

Fig. 7.
FE meshes of multi-cell plain-woven composites for high-performance computation.

Fig. 8.
Vertical displacement of plain-woven composites under a bending loading.

SUMMARY

A 3-D computational model based on the textile preforming process was developed for the 3-D complex-architected textile composites. The FE model for the complex yarn & matrix geometries was generated by using the digital element method, yarn smoothing, CAD solid modeling and finite element meshing. The 3-D geometries for 2-D and 3-D woven and triaxial braided composites were created with the present method. The model has yarn-level microgeometry. Therefore, yarns and matrix materials can be discretely modeled without any homogenization, which may be critical to accurately characterize the damage mechanism in the textile composites.

By integrating the enhanced 3-D computational model and the high-performance computation with the parallel clustered computers and the parallelly enhanced FE structural analysis program, the present work presents a novel procedure for the property prediction and damage characterization of the textile composites. The method can be utilized for the prediction under both the static and dynamic loadings including impact analysis where the damage behavior highly depends on the local microstructure of the textile composites.

The present model integrates the weaving process simulation with the stress/damage analysis modules. The model can provide a methodology to directly assess the effect of fabrication parameters on the performance of the textile composites such as variable cross section of the reinforcing yarns, process-induced microcracking, fatigue life, damage progression, etc. The present model will further be developed to incorporate manufacturing variability and the effects of defects including process induced microcracking infused by a resin transfer molding (RTM) and the similar processes.

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